

Phytochemical and antioxidant properties of *Anemia wightiana* leaf extracts

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Abstract : Medicinal plants are natural sources for several medicinal products. Since ancient time, traditionally plants use to treat numerous human and animal ailments. *Anemia wightiana* (Family : Anemiaceae) commonly called as 'doradilla' which traditionally used to treat tuberculosis and exhibits antimicrobial activity. The aim of the present study was focused on phytochemical investigation, such as total phenolic, flavonoid, tannin content determination and *in vitro* antioxidant activity like, DPPH, hydroxide and nitric oxide radical scavenging activity of various solvents (hexane, chloroform and methanol) leaf extracts of *Anemia wightiana*. Methanol extract was found to be a good source for most of the tested phytoconstituents as well as harbor highly potent antioxidant properties with least IC₅₀ values (74.32, 35.41 and 33.81 mg/ml for DPPH, OH and NO radical activity respectively). The results of GC-MS analysis of methanolic extract revealed the presence of 81 compounds. The results of present study revealed bioactive compounds and antioxidant potential of methanol extract of *Anemia wightiana* which requires deep investigation in isolation of active principles to get plant based antioxidant agents.

Keywords : *Anemia wightiana*, antioxidant, GC-MS analysis.

Introduction

Since ancient time plant based products have been used in the health care systems of several human communities. Numerous plant genera are used in traditional medicine in different countries. Indian systems of herbal medicine use around 8,000 species. In India 1500 drugs are extracted from various plants used in curing human ailments¹. Plants are rich source of alternative antioxidant agents. Recently, plant secondary metabolites such as phenols, flavonoids, tannins and terpenoids have received extensive attention due to their important physiological properties especially, in antioxidant and antimicrobial activities². Several previous reports stated that the herbal medicines are still used by most of the human communities as a principal healthcare with least side effects³.

Free radicals are reactive species with very short span of half-life; high react with macromolecules like proteins, lipids and DNA and causes damages. Antioxidant property containing compound are basically understood to fight against free radicals in living systems. The toxicity activity of free radicals can be counteracted by some cellular antioxidant defense system present in the body. Hence, human body will be in requirement of antioxidant con-

taining food stuffs and herbals. Many commercially available synthetic antioxidants are withdrawn due to their toxic nature. Hence, there is renewed interest in the exploration and use of plant products as high potent antioxidant agents. *Anemia wightiana* (Family : Anemiaceae) was used in treatment of tuberculosis and also it exhibits strong antimicrobial activity⁴. Species of this genus contains several essential oil and terpenes⁵. The aim of the work was to examine the antioxidant potential, qualitative, quantitative phytochemical analysis and GC-MS analysis of various organic solvents (hexane, chloroform and methanol) leaf extracts of *Anemia wightiana*.

Results and discussion

The results of preliminary phytochemical analysis in various solvent extracts of *Anemia wightiana* leaf revealed the presence of saponins, phenols, tannins, glycosides, flavonoids, steroids, alkaloids, terpenoids, carbohydrates, proteins and oils (Table 1). In methanol extract, most of the tested phytochemicals were copiously present. Hexane extract contained high amount of oils and fats whereas, other contents were slightly present. Methanol extract possessed high quantity of phenolic compounds (125.27 µg/mg of extract), flavonoid (85.97 µg/mg of extract)

Table 1. Phytochemical analysis of various solvent leaf extracts of *Anemia wightiana*

Sr. no.	Phytoconstituents	Hexane	Chloroform	Methanol
1.	Alkaloids	++	++	+
2.	Flavonoids	+	+	++
3.	Cardiac glycosides	+	-	+
4.	Tannins/Phenolics	++	+	+
5.	Lignins	-	-	-
6.	Amino acids/Proteins	-	+++	+++
7.	Steroids	++	++	+
8.	Carbohydrates	+	+	++
9.	Saponins	-	-	+
10.	Terpenoids	-	+	+
11.	Fats/Oils	+	-	-
12.	Anthocyanins	+	+	++
13.	Leucoanthocyanins	+	+	++

+++ = Copiously present, ++ = Moderately present, + = Slightly present, - = Absent.

properties than other extracts in all tested methods. The inhibition reactions appeared still even, at the highest tested concentration (1.0 mg/ml). At this concentration, methanol extract achieved more than 89.41%, 86.85%, 86.06% inhibition of radicals with least IC₅₀ values 74.32, 35.41 and 33.81 µg/ml in DPPH, OH and NO radicals respectively. A weak pattern of scavenging capacity was observed in chloroform and hexane extracts of the *Anemia wightiana* with high IC₅₀ values. The three extracts with the highest radical-scavenging capacity were in the order : methanol > chloroform > hexane.

The result of GC-MS analysis of methanol extract showed the presence of 81 compounds (Fig. 4). Among the 81 compounds, 5 phenolic compounds namely ferulic acid (RT : 12.06, 0.84%), benzene-1,2,3-triol (RT : 15.11, 6.72%), aspidinol (RT : 15.73, 4.12%), gallic

Table 2. Determination of phytoconstituents of various solvent leaf extracts of *Anemia wightiana*

Sr. no.	Phytoconstituents (µg/mg extract) ^a	Hexane	Chloroform	Methanol
1.	Phenol content	18.71 ± 0.39 ^a	52.53 ± 1.18 ^b	125.27 ± 1.21 ^c
2.	Flavonoid content	22.87 ± 1.51 ^a	31.21 ± 0.90 ^b	85.97 ± 0.55 ^c
3.	Tannin content	10.78 ± 1.92 ^a	55.22 ± 1.92 ^b	115.22 ± 1.92 ^c

^aData represent the mean ± S.D (n = 3). Mean values of each row followed by different superscript letter (a-c) differs in their effectiveness (c > b > a) when subject to Tukey's multiple comparison test (p < 0.05).

and tannin (115.22 µg/mg of extract) content (Table 2).

The radical-scavenging activities of the extracts depicted a dose-response relationship (Figs. 1, 2 and 3). Methanol extracts had significantly higher antioxidant

acid (RT : 17.14, 43.67%) and 4-ethyl-2-methoxyphenol (RT : 19.01, 1.20%) occurred abundantly. These compounds may be responsible for antioxidant activities of the extract. Numerous secondary metabolites are synthe-

Fig. 1. DPPH radical scavenging activity (*p < 0.05).

Fig. 2. Nitric oxide radical scavenging activity (*p < 0.05).

Fig. 3. Hydroxide radical scavenging activity (* $p < 0.05$).

Fig. 4. Chromatogram obtained from the GC-MS analysis.

sized by plants for several purposes i.e. as herbivores, toxicity, antimicrobial agents, etc.⁶. Plant phenolic components (flavonoids and tannins) act as high potent antioxidants or free radical scavengers among the various types of secondary metabolites⁷. The phytochemical screening and antioxidant activity of *Anemia wightiana* infuse that it may be used in traditional medicines.

Materials and methods :

Plant collection and extract preparation :

Fresh, matured *Anemia wightiana* leaf samples were collected from Shevaroy Hills, Yercaud, Salem District, Tamilnadu. The collected plant material was authenticated by Dr. K. Nandakumar, Head of the Department, Systematic Taxonomist, Kandaswami Kandar's College, Paramathi Velur, Namakkal District, Tamilnadu. Powdered leaf sample was extracted sequentially by using

various solvents in increasing polarity (hexane, chloroform and methanol) manner in Soxhlet for 48 h. The extractives from the plant material were dried completely and stored at 4 °C for further investigations.

Phytochemical screening and antioxidant activity :

The extracts were subjected to qualitative identification phytochemical constituents⁸, quantitative determination of total phenolic⁹, flavonoid⁹, tannin¹⁰, DPPH¹¹, nitric oxide¹² and hydroxide radical scavenging activities¹³ by using the methods.

GC-MS analysis :

The GC-MS analysis of leaf methanol extract of *Anemia wightiana* was carried out in a CP3800 Saturn 2200 Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometer (GC-MS) system. The temperature programs were 80 to 350 °C at the rate of 3 °C/min and held at 350 °C at 35 min. Ion source temperature was 200 °C and scan range was 20–500 amu. The identification of unknown components of extract was done by comparing their mass spectra with the spectrum of known components stored in the Wiley and NIST libraries.

Statistical analysis :

All experiments were done in triplicates and the data were analyzed using one way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) by SPSS (16.0 versions) at $p < 0.05$ ¹⁴.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of present investigation we may conclude that methanol leaf extract of *Anemia wightiana* possess promising sources of both primary and secondary metabolites and also contains potent antioxidant bioactive principles. The isolation, purification and structural elucidations of bioactive compounds will be carried out in future. The isolation of phytochemical constituents may possess pharmacological importance which might serve as a safe antioxidant against free radical mediated diseases.

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